

Pricing liquidity for Lightning wallets

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Abstract

Bitcoin banks that interoperate on the Lightning network are the most developed path to scaling Bitcoin for mass adoption. One problem faced by these banks is the implementation of fees for transactions that incur protocol fees on the Bitcoin and Lightning networks. This problem is particularly important in the context of providing both onchain and offchain liquidity, since different usage patterns can incur dramatically different protocol fees. We argue that the possibility of liquidity arbitrage on the Lightning network sets a market rate for inbound liquidity, and use an estimate of this market rate to develop new fee structures that properly price liquidity without overcharging everyday users. Furthermore, we perform simulations using historical transaction data from users of the Bitcoin Beach Wallet, and show that the new fee structures are able to account for different usage patterns under realistic conditions.

1 Introduction

Bitcoin has a fundamental scaling ceiling set by the requirement for global broadcast and verification of every transaction, onchain. The Lightning network allows transactions to remain offchain by allowing users to route bitcoin through onchain-settled payment channels (Poon and Dryja, 2015). Although the Lightning network significantly improves Bitcoin’s scalability, the remaining requirement for onchain transactions to open and close each payment channel, means that further scaling improvements will be necessary to accommodate mass adoption (Burchert et al., 2017).

Custodial Bitcoin banks, that interoperate on the Lightning network, could accommodate mass adoption. Custodial banks allow users to trade-off Bitcoin’s pseudonymous privacy, permissionlessness, and censorship resistance for access to Bitcoin’s open monetary network, and deflationary monetary policy. Importantly, this trade-off may be improved in the future with the development of technologies like hosted channels with private routing (Kumaigorodski, 2021), and federated Chaumian mints (Sirion, 2021).

One challenge faced by custodial Bitcoin banks is the implementation of transaction fees. Through batching, intelligent liquidity management, and intralegder trans-

actions, banks can substantially reduce the fee burden of interacting with the Bitcoin network for their users, but they can not eliminate it entirely. To the extent that the bank interfaces with the wider Bitcoin network it will incur protocol fees that will ultimately have to be paid for by users of the bank. Fee structures that account for the real costs of each user’s transactions, would allow banks to be more permissionless, serving customers with different transactional needs while staying competitive and sustainable. This is particularly important in the context of offering users full liquidity for both onchain and offchain transactions, where different usage habits can incur dramatically different protocol fees.

Here, we address the problem of implementing transaction fees that properly price Lightning liquidity. We discuss the costs of managing onchain and offchain liquidity in the Lightning network. We argue that the possibility of inbound liquidity arbitrage ensures the emergence of a market rate for inbound liquidity. Using an estimate of this market rate, we develop fee structures that account for a user’s transaction history when pricing liquidity. And finally, we study how these fee structures would impact real users through simulation, using data from users of the Bitcoin Beach Wallet.

2 Background

2.1 Payment channels and liquidity

To transact on the Lightning network, users commit bitcoin to payment channels. The bitcoin in these channels can be used to route and send offchain payments but not to transact onchain. Thus, the user’s total balance of bitcoin will not always be immediately liquid for both onchain and offchain transactions.

The native way of managing onchain and offchain liquidity on the Lightning network is by opening and closing payment channels. To acquire more offchain outbound liquidity, a user can peg-*in*¹ to the Lightning network by opening a channel between their node and a counterparty’s. Opening a channel requires that a user commit bitcoin to a 2-of-2 multisignature contract with a counterparty that is connected to the network and willing to

¹Following convention, we use *-in* to refer to transactions that move bitcoin into the Lightning network, and *-out* to refer to transactions that move bitcoin out of the Lightning network.

route the user’s payments. The bitcoin in the new channel is typically provided entirely by the user that opens the channel, so the counterparty risks little in accepting. Moreover, if the user has additional connections to the rest of the network the counterparty gains inbound liquidity by accepting the channel. Thus, it is usually easy for users to find willing counterparties.

To acquire more onchain liquidity, a user can *peg-out* of the Lightning network by closing a channel. Unlike opening a channel, closing a channel does not require permission from the counterparty (though cooperation from the counterparty is preferable, since, otherwise, the user’s bitcoin will be unspendable for length of the lock-time). In either case, closing a channel reduces the user’s *and the counterparty’s* offchain inbound and outbound liquidity. Thus, unlike opening a channel, closing a channel negatively impacts the counterparty.

Finally, to acquire more offchain inbound liquidity, the user needs a peer to commit *their* bitcoin to a new channel and be willing and able to route payments to the user. This can happen spontaneously if the peer expects to be able to collect routing fees from the channel. Alternatively, users can negotiate reciprocal channel openings with semi-trusted peers², or pay for inbound liquidity by buying channel leases or committing to dual funded channels (Osuntokun et al., 2020; Neigut, 2018). In each of these cases, the benefits of the channel for the counterparty must outweigh the costs of the onchain transaction and capital allocation required to open and maintain the channel.

Two additional operations are in development that would allow users to manage onchain and offchain liquidity without opening and closing channels. Channel splicing (Russell, 2018) would allow users to *peg-out* by reducing a channel’s total capacity without closing it, thereby maintaining its inbound capacity. PeerSwap (Togami and Nick, 2021) would allow channel partners to trustlessly swap offchain bitcoin on the channel for onchain bitcoin and additional inbound capacity. Both splicing and PeerSwap will reduce the onchain costs of acquiring inbound liquidity by allowing users to maintain, or increase, inbound liquidity on existing channels, rather than always paying the onchain fees for opening new channels.

The different channel operations discussed above also have second-order effects. On the Lightning network, a user’s history of channel management operations is broadcast globally and cryptographically verifiable. Other users need this information to route payments, but it may also affect the choices they make when setting routing fees and choosing potential channel counterparties. Operations that negatively impact counterparties, like closing channels or splicing-out, will negatively affect the user’s reputation on the network. All else being

²This can happen through informal chat groups like Rings of Fire (<https://t.me/theRingsOfFire>) or PlebNet (<https://t.me/plebnet>) or on platforms designed for the purpose like Lightning Network Plus (<https://lightningnetwork.plus/>).

equal, the profitability of a channel depends on its lifetime (Brânzei et al., 2017). Thus, among other considerations, peers will prefer to open new channels with users that have a history of long-lived channels and counterparties will set higher fees to users that have a history of short-lived channels.

2.2 Submarine swaps

The costs of closing channels, and the challenges of acquiring additional inbound liquidity, have motivated the development of alternative methods of managing onchain and offchain liquidity. “Submarine” swaps (Bosworth, 2018) are the most widely adopted such alternative. Swap services, like Boltz³ and Loop⁴, operate Lightning network nodes that trustlessly pay offchain invoices in exchange for onchain bitcoin (swap-in); or send onchain bitcoin in exchange for offchain payments (swap-out).

Submarine swaps have all the benefits of PeerSwaps with the difference that the swap is with a central service node rather than a channel counterparty. This adds a requirement for routing to complete a submarine swap, which increases the cost of swapping but also provides several benefits. One is that, by using a multi path payment, the liquidity on multiple channels can be swapped in a single operation. Another benefit is that the routing requirement ensures that the inbound liquidity gained by swapping-out is fully available to route payments (at least as far as the swap node). This dramatically simplifies to process of acquiring inbound liquidity, since the user no longer needs to determine whether their counterparty would be willing and able to route their payments (ZmnSCPxj, 2020).

Submarine swaps are trustless and some implementations are open source. The only barrier to starting a new submarine swap service is the capital needed to ensure a stock of onchain and offchain liquidity to offer customers. This means that there is little to limit competition driving swap fees to the lowest sustainable rates. Behind the scenes, submarine swap services rely on the same native operations of opening, closing, and acquiring new channels to manage their onchain and offchain liquidity.⁵ Thus, we can expect that the costs of using submarine swap services will approach the costs of the equivalent channel operations, with additional costs due to the capital allocation and the need to route funds to (or from) the service node. Submarine swaps are useful, not because they reduce fees, but because they allow their users to trustlessly out-source liquidity management channel operations.

³<https://boltz.exchange/>

⁴<https://Lightning.engineering/loop/>

⁵While large swap services may be able to batch onchain channel operations more efficiently than users, each swap requires an onchain output. This requirement limits the extent to which large swap services will be able to offer lower fees for their service than what the user could get by performing the equivalent channel operations.

Table 1: Trustless swap-out fees for Loop and Boltz. The base and proportional routing fees are estimated from the capacity-weighted, median channel fees of all open inbound channels on January 31, 2022.

	Routing (sat, %)	Swap (%)
Boltz	0.00, 0.01	0.5
Loop	1.00, 0.22	0.1*

* The average fee quoted by the `loop quote` command from October, through December, 2021.

Table 1 shows the swap service fees and estimated Lightning network routing fees for swapping-out using Boltz and Loop (the onchain fee will be roughly the same for both services and depend on the current demand for blockspace rather than the amount swapped). The two services charge very different fees but, in practice, the total costs are similar: Boltz’s high swap fees are balanced by Loop’s high routing fees. We can begin to understand the difference between the two services by noting that Loop’s channels are significantly shorter lived than Boltz’ and the rest of the Lightning network’s (Figure 1). Moreover, Loop’s high routing fees are not a transient phenomenon; routing to Loop’s node has been consistently more expensive than the Lightning network average through periods of high and low onchain fees (Figure 2). Loop’s unique routing characteristics are not unexpected. Short lived channels with high incoming fees are one of the costs of managing liquidity through channel operations and, by providing submarine swaps, Loop bears this burden in place of the nodes it swaps with.

2.3 Inbound liquidity arbitrage

To explain Boltz’s long channel lifetimes and low incoming routing fees it suffices to notice that since Boltz charges a higher swap fee, it can out-source *its* channel management operations to Loop. Boltz can keep the routing fees to its node low, by charging a swap fee that is at least as high as the sum of the Loop swap fee and routing fees to the Loop node. Stated another way, Boltz can outsource its channel operations if the routing nodes between Boltz and Loop are willing to sell *their* inbound liquidity to Boltz for, at most, the difference between the two services’ swap fees. The balance between Boltz’s high swap fees and Loop’s high routing fees is maintained by the possibility of arbitrage by routing nodes.

This inbound liquidity arbitrage is a general phenomenon across the Lightning network. When any entity offers inbound liquidity at a rate lower than the routing fees to Loop (or another inbound liquidity sink), a routing node can profit by acquiring that inbound liquidity and opening a matching channel to Loop. This is most clearly illustrated in the market for inbound channel creation, where the arbitrage is simplest. Table 2 shows the channel creation fees charged by different Lightning network service providers. The fees are all at least as high as

Figure 1: Current (above) and historical (below) channel lifetimes for Loop and Boltz. Capacity weighted distributions of lifetimes for channels connected to the two submarine swap services, and across the rest of the Lightning network. Lines show capacity weighted medians. Historical data from fiatjaf (2022).

what one could expect to make by routing to Loop, and the lifetimes are all sufficient to exhaust a channel’s entire capacity before the channel is closed by Loop (Figure 1). Figure 2 shows the historical fees for inbound channel creation available on Pool and the liquidity ad market. During the first half of 2021, it may have been possible for routing nodes to buy channels from Pool and sell the inbound liquidity to Loop’s customer’s at a profit (though this is uncertain since it’s possible that Pool’s service fee was higher during this time). Since then, the prices for inbound liquidity on Loop and Pool have reached what appears to be an equilibrium.

Another way of acquiring additional inbound liquidity is by trading-out using custodial services, that allow both onchain and offchain deposits and withdrawals. Since selling inbound liquidity is not the primary purpose of these services, it may be possible to find conditions under which acquiring inbound liquidity using a custodial service is cheaper in terms of fees than using a trustless swap service. Table 3 shows estimates for the routing fees associated with depositing offchain bitcoin to several custodial services as well as the service fees for on-chain withdrawals and a summary of KYC requirements for each service. When compared to Tables 1 and 2, it is clear that some of these custodial services offer much cheaper inbound liquidity than other services. For many routing node operators, this could represent an attractive arbitrage opportunity. On the other hand, using a custodial service comes with additional costs and limitations, such as: custody risk; privacy; deposit, withdraw, and balance limits; and terms of use restrictions. Moreover,

Figure 2: Historical inbound liquidity fees. Weekly capacity and duration weighted* incoming proportional routing fees for channels connected to Loop and the across the rest of the Lightning network (data from fiatjaf, 2022); are plotted on the same scale as the node capacity weighted proportional fees offered on liquidity ads (data from Decker, 2021); and the volume weighted cleared proportional fees charged by Pool (data from Kollider, 2022)†. The lower panel shows onchain fees for comparison. Shaded regions show 25% and 75% quantiles. Data for liquidity ad leases is not plotted where historical gossip message archives are unavailable.

* Since fees can be updated over the course of a channel’s lifetime, the medians and quantiles are calculated with weights determined by the product of the channel’s capacity and the amount of time between updates.

† Lease rates for Pool and liquidity ads are not annualized since the minimum lease times are sufficient for an inbound liquidity arbitrage.

Table 2: Lightning service provider fees for inbound channel creation. Lifetime refers to the minimum lifetime of the channel, it may stay open longer than that.

	Creation (sat, %)	Lifetime	Atomic
Boltz	0, 1.50*	—	yes
LNBIG	4500, 0.21†	1 month	no
lnd-routing	500, 0.25	1 month	no
Liquidity ads	612, 0.42‡	1 month	yes
Pool	0, 0.25§	§	yes
Thor	10,425, 1.11	1 month	no

* Boltz charges a 0.5% fee for swapping-in, if the user does not have enough inbound capacity to receive the swapped-in funds, Boltz creates a channel with an additional capacity of 25% inbound liquidity.

† This fee does not include the cost of the channel creation transaction.

‡ Node-capacity-weighted medians calculated on February 16, 2022. Does not include the cost of the channel creation transaction.

§ In addition to this fee, Pool charges a service fee of 0.05% - 0.25%; half of the channel creating transaction fee; and a, one time, 1,000 satoshi flat fee. Channel lifetimes are enforced onchain and available for 2, 4, or 12 weeks or 1 year.

since custodial services need to maintain inbound liquidity to receive payments, they may implement additional measures to prevent this kind of arbitrage.

3 Liquidity fee structures

The primary purpose of a Bitcoin bank is to facilitate transactions for its users. To accomplish this in a competitive way, a bank must, among other things, maintain sufficient onchain and offchain liquidity. We define the

Table 3: Custodial service fees for inbound liquidity. None of these services charge deposit fees. The base and proportional routing fees are estimated from the capacity weighted median channel fees of all inbound channels to each service’s node(s) on January 31, 2022.

	Routing (sat, %)	Withdraw (sat, %)	KYC
Bitfinex	1.00, 0.05	40000, 0.0	email
Buda	0.50, 0.01	5000, 0.0	full
OKX	1.00, 0.01	20000, 0.0	full
River	1.00, 0.05	0, 0.0*	full
Bitcoin Beach			
Wallet	0.00, 0.01	2000, 0.0*	phone
Blue Wallet	1.00, 0.05	0, 0.5*	none
coins	1.00, 0.05	0, 0.0*	none
Strike	1.00, 0.01	0, 0.0*	full
Wallet of Satoshi	1.00, 0.02	— †	none

* These fees do not include the cost of the onchain transaction.

† The onchain withdraw fee formula for Wallet of Satoshi is not public.

loop imbalance as the difference between the bank’s onchain liquidity and offchain outbound liquidity. The loop imbalance will be positive when the bank has too much onchain liquidity (and not enough offchain outbound liquidity) and negative when the bank is running out of onchain liquidity (and also running out of offchain inbound liquidity). Thus, to state the above in a different way, a Bitcoin bank must keep its loop imbalance within a small window determined by the liquidity requirements of its users.

Some users will have outsized effects on the bank’s loop imbalance. For example, a merchant that routinely

receives offchain payments, and periodically withdraws bitcoin from their account onchain, will impart a consistently negative rate of change on the bank’s loop imbalance. Unless this usage is balanced by users with opposite effects on the bank’s loop imbalance, the bank will eventually have to swap out to rebalance its onchain and offchain liquidity and regain some inbound liquidity.

A bank that wants to serve users in a permissionless way, and remain sustainable, will need to implement a fee structure that reflects the impact of each user’s activity on the bank’s loop imbalance. The following sections introduce specific formulae that meet this requirement and discuss them with regard to sustainability and user experience.

3.1 Idealized fee structures

Let, x_i be the loop imbalance created by a user’s i th transaction, $f(x_i)$ be the fee collected by the bank for that transaction, and $l(x_i)$ be the market rate for correcting the imbalance using a swap service (see Table 1).

A simple way to limit imbalance would be to charge the market imbalance correction rate for each transaction:

$$f(x_i) = l(x_i) \tag{1}$$

From the perspective of user experience, this approach trades high fees for simplicity. It does not account for the balancing effects of a user’s previous or future transactions, and therefore over-charges users ($|\sum x| \leq \sum |x|$).

A smoother dynamic fee formula would take into account a user’s previous transactions, $1, \dots, i-1$, and charge users less if their current transaction balanced their previous transactions. Consider the following formula:

$$f(x_i) = l(x_i) + l\left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} x_j\right) - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} f(x_j) \tag{2}$$

where the fee determined by the market rate for a swap service $l(x_i)$, is smoothed by accounting for the user’s running difference between the market rate for correcting their net imbalance, $l\left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} x_j\right)$, and total fees paid, $\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} f(x_j)$. We can get a sense of the iterated effect of this formula, by rearranging terms:

$$\sum_{j=1}^i f(x_j) = l(x_i) + l\left(\sum_{j=1}^{i-1} x_j\right) \tag{3}$$

to show that the formula ensures that the total fees paid by a user, approaches the net market loop rate with a deviation due only to the most recent transaction.

3.2 User experience constrains fees

Loop imbalance will be affected by every onchain and offchain transaction. Yet, users have predefined expectations for the kinds of fees that these different types of

transactions ought to have. In the Bitcoin ecosystem, it is generally accepted that the sender pays the transaction fee. In the case of making retail payments, this expectation conflicts with that of traditional banking where merchants are usually charged a fee for receiving money from customers. Conforming to these expectations is likely to improve user experience, but leaves a Bitcoin bank few places where fees can be charged.

A common solution is to implement bank fees only for onchain payments (like Wallet of Satoshi and the Bitcoin Beach Wallet). This compromise maintains the “sender pays the fee” expectation from the Bitcoin ecosystem while approximating the free retail payments experience of traditional banking with low-cost offchain fees. Unfortunately, implementing a liquidity imbalance fee for only one side of the imbalance flow could have undesirable side effects. For example, since a large deposit into the bank would create a correspondingly large imbalance without accruing a fee, Formula 2 would charge a big fee for the next onchain payment transaction, no matter its size.

One possible mediation for this would be to introduce a cap on the maximum, above market, fee rate. Consider the formula:

$$f(x_i) = \max\left(\nu l(x_i), \min\left(\mu l(x_i), \hat{f}(x_i)\right)\right) \tag{4}$$

where \hat{f} is Formula 2, above. The result is a self-balancing fee formula with transaction fees capped to be no more than μ , and no less than ν , times the market fee rate for loop imbalance correction. For everyday users, with low total imbalance, $l(\sum x) \approx 0$, most transactions would only be charged the minimum fee rate, $\nu l(x_i)$. Moreover, some odd, high-imbalance transactions would also have the same minimum fee since the additional fees paid by low-imbalance transactions would be included in the calculation of the difference between total fees paid and net market loop rate. In the same way, the fee correction after a large deposit would proceed at a maximum rate determined by μ rather than happening all at once.⁶

4 Historical transaction replay

To understand how these different fee structures may perform in a realistic usage context, we analyzed a historical transaction dataset of Bitcoin Beach Wallet users in the second half of 2021. We replay the transactions under different fee structures and calculate what the fees charged to users would have been, and how that compares to the users’ impact on loop imbalance. In Figure 3 we plot two complimentary ways of looking at the consequences of different fee structures: (Left column) fees per transaction as function of the transaction’s effect on loop imbalance (note the logarithmic scales), and (Right column)

⁶We note that further elaborations to the formula will be necessary to account for the full array of a Bitcoin bank’s operational costs (e.g. maintaining a sufficient capital stock of onchain and offchain liquidity). That discussion is left for future work.

Figure 3: Fee structures applied to a historical dataset of transactions on the Bitcoin Beach Wallet during the second half of 2021. The left column shows the bank fee as a function of the loop imbalance created by the transaction under the different fee formulae. Only onchain payment transactions are shown, all other transactions are free except for protocol fees. The right column shows all onchain and offchain transactions plotted according to the initiating user’s cumulative effect on loop imbalance at the time of the transaction. Plots on the right column are cropped to show a maximum loop imbalance of one bitcoin in either direction. Gray lines show the modeled market rate for loop imbalance correction, $l(\cdot)$. Transactions above the market rate lines, overpay for their individual effect on loop imbalance (left), or belong to users that have overpaid for their cumulative effect on loop imbalance (right).

cumulative fees collected per transaction as a function of the user’s net loop imbalance. Gray lines on each panel allow us to contrast the transaction fees collected with the modeled market rates for loop imbalance correction. When a user’s transaction happens below these lines, the user is creating an imbalance that the bank may have to correct at its own expense.

Since fee structures will impact user behavior, we must note that the predictive power of these transaction replay simulations diminishes as the fee structures we simulate get further from the fee structure that was in place when the transactions were made. The Bitcoin Beach Wallet only charges a bank fee above the protocol fee for onchain payments. Thus, in our simulations, we applied fees according to Formula 1 and Formula 2 only to onchain payments. Furthermore, instead of using Formula 4, we used a similarly intentioned, but less distant formula in Figure 3:

$$f(x_i) = \max\left(2000, \min\left(\kappa l(x_i), \hat{f}(x_i)\right)\right) \quad (5)$$

where, again, \hat{f} is Formula 2 above.

The first row of Figure 3 shows the imbalance fee structure currently implemented in the Bitcoin Beach Wallet: a flat 2,000 satoshi bank fee on onchain payments. The right column of that first row shows that most users have a negative impact on the bank’s loop imbalance and that only a few pay the market rate to correct that imbalance. The transactions above the market rate lines belong to users that overpay for their liquidity imbalance, making many onchain payments while maintaining a low net imbalance. The transactions below the market rate lines belong to users that underpay for their liquidity imbalance, receiving large amounts of bitcoin offchain but only rarely paying onchain.

Comparing the different fee formulae proposed here, we see that only the self-balancing formulae have the effect of keeping most transactions at or above the market rate lines. As expected, the simplest self-balancing formula, Formula 2, does the best job at charging users exactly as much fees as the imbalance they create costs. However, we can see that the simple self-balancing Formula 2 has significantly more variable fees than the naive Formula 1. The self-balancing fee structure described in Formula 5, appears to have a good balance of predictability and proper pricing even when applied only to onchain payments. This fee structure, with maximum fee rate limited to twice the market rate, would result in a flat fees for 98% of onchain payments and allow 94% of users to only ever be charged a flat fee.

5 Discussion

This work was motivated by the discovery that a few users of the Bitcoin Beach Wallet were using the wallet as a fee-efficient way of acquiring additional inbound liquidity. This activity had the effect of consistently reducing the bank’s onchain liquidity and offchain inbound

liquidity. The problem was made worse by the fact that the Bitcoin Beach Wallet, operates with significant constraints on total liquidity because most reserves are kept illiquid, in cold storage. To the extent that the bank’s ability to process transactions for its users was affected, it was necessary to pay for a swap service to restore onchain liquidity and inbound liquidity. The current market rate for inbound liquidity on the Lightning network is not trivial. Although, protocol developments like splicing and PeerSwap will reduce some of the costs associated with acquiring additional inbound liquidity, the cost of inbound capital allocation is likely to remain significant.

We described several fee structures that account for each user’s impact on the bank’s onchain and offchain liquidity balance. Since these fee structures assure that the fees paid by a user asymptotically approach the market cost of inbound liquidity, their implementation will remove the opportunity of arbitrage. We verified through a simulation study, that formulae that keep track of a user’s net contribution to imbalance between onchain and offchain liquidity and total fees paid, do a good job of charging users appropriate fees in realistic scenarios. And we showed that limiting these self-balancing fee structures can ensure a relatively simple user experience.

Finally, the fee structures discussed here may have applications outside of custodial Bitcoin banks. Non-custodial Lightning wallets like Phoenix⁷ and Breez⁸, use submarine swap services to enable their users to participate in onchain transactions. This is equivalent to a custodial wallet using the fee structure described in Formula 1. The fee structures described here could be used by a new submarine swap service to sustainably reduce the fee burden of everyday non-custodial Lightning wallet users.

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